

ETHNOPSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF FAMILY DISPUTES

Eshmurodov Olmos Elamonivich

Associate Professor of the "Psychology"
Department of Termiz State Pedagogical Institute,
Doctor of Philosophy in Psychology (PhD)

Annatatsion: Usually, information about a speech, a word, a dispute comes out of one mouth, and as time passes, its details increase. Its scope expands as the number of participants who are aware of it and are involved in it increases, moving away from the source of information.

Key words: family, husband, wife, word, person, form, method, asset,

When a husband or wife often talks about it to a third person after they have a dispute, they speak on one side as much as possible in order to make themselves innocent and right in this dispute, to sway this person to protect their interests. In this case, the subject uses almost all verbal and non-verbal means of speech, tone, gestures, facial expressions, accent, etc. to ensure that the incident (conflict) is more exaggerated than its original state. The more people are told about the conflict, the more it escalates and the consequences can be tragic.

There are conjunctive (constructive) and divisive (destructive) forms of conflict. Therefore, young people should be prepared for bonding conflicts that occur in family life, learn to effectively use the bonding opportunities of such conflicts, and not to turn them into conflicts with negative consequences. In most cases, the constructive conflicts that arise in the relationship of the spouses lead to the resolution of the conflicts between the spouses, the emergence of cooperation between them, and ultimately to the strengthening of the marital relationship.

As we have mentioned above in separation disputes, the resolution of one dispute (that is, the satisfaction of the interests of one of the spouses) creates the basis for the emergence of another dispute, and family life becomes a "continuous battlefield" for the couple. Such a conflict environment has a serious impact not only on the mental world of the couple in this family, their nerves, health, and social status, but also on the psyche of the children born in these families and brought up in the same environment. The conflict situation, constant quarrels, lack of kindness in such families can manifest its complications not only in these families, but also in the families of the next generation to be formed by the

children of this family.

Four types of families are formed as a result of the development of couple relations in newly created families. These are the following:

- a) families with strengthened mutual relations;
- b) families whose relations are temporarily strengthened;
- c) new conflicts arise and repeat (conflict) families;
- g) families whose relations are interrupted and separated.

Among them, the most acceptable are families of type 1. Each of our young people should strive to build such a strong family. Type 2 families are families whose relationships are temporarily strengthened. After the disputes in such families, if the spouses draw the correct conclusions from the disputes and conflicts, realize their mistakes in time, and try to understand each other, mutual cooperation can also occur in them. . If married couples do not have enough knowledge and experience to understand their mistakes and correct them, or if they do not want to eliminate these mistakes, as well as their older relatives and friends, based on their rich life experiences, they can give the right guidance and advice to young people. if they don't, if they seem to interfere inappropriately in the life of a young family (unfortunately, such situations often occur in Uzbek families), in such cases, the temporary peace achieved may be destroyed by the emergence of new conflicts.

The third type of family is the most characteristic of the four types of families and requires serious attention. Because in some families (type 4), there is a high probability that the couple's relationship will break down due to bad relations, deepening of conflicts, aggravation of tensions. Of course, the event of divorce is sad for family-marital relations. Especially in such cases, if there are children in the family, they are left without a father or a mother. After the divorce, the social situation of both parties becomes tense. But a person whose family broke up for the first time may correct his mistakes the next time, and may later "find his match" and lead a happy life.

However, another aspect characteristic of the Uzbek ethnic group is that the Uzbeks, as well as the Tajiks, Kyrgyz, and Kazakhs, have a strong tradition of having a negative attitude towards the breakdown of families as expressed in other nations. That is, divorce is condemned according to public opinion. In addition, consanguineous marriages are more common in Uzbek families than in families of other ethnic groups. In such families, if the couple's relationship does not develop as expected, i.e., they are conflicted, do not understand each other, do not match

each other, and cannot reconcile psychologically, how can they act in such a way as to "do not break the family", "do not break the ties of kinship" trying to save families no matter what.

At present, most of the unpleasant events that occur in the field of marriage and family relations, various nervous disorders, the origin of diseases, various crimes, murders, suicides, treason, children's upbringing, and many other disappointments fall on these 3rd type families. Therefore, it is desirable that not only our youth, but also officials whose work is directly related to marriage and family problems, community, authorities, and adults should have relevant information about the socio-psychological characteristics of the modern family, marital conflicts, and the psychology of family conflicts. Young people should have the necessary knowledge and information about marital disputes, their prevention and elimination.

Conflicts can also arise between parents and children, and the following serve as a basis for such disagreements:

1. Failure to take into account the existing difference between worldviews;
2. Young people's independent organization of free time, choice of friends, feelings, clothes, career, and life partner are sometimes unwelcome to parents;
3. Parent's addiction to alcohol or morally inferior persons;
4. In some children, the skills of working are not formed and as a result they get used to living a light-hearted life;
5. Some young people forget their filial duty;
6. Inadequate levels of psychological and pedagogical knowledge of parents, etc.

As a result of the above-mentioned deficiencies in the relationship between parents and children, the family loses its sense of well-being and coldness occurs. What do you say to the fact that there are children who even drink and raise their hands to their parents, let alone not fulfilling their filial duty, and those who are light-hearted people who turn their parents face to the ground?

Some parents do not know the periods of age crisis that inevitably occur in children at the age of 3, 6, 13-14. At these age stages, new psychological changes occur in the child's psyche. This is evident in their relationships with adults, including parents. Some parents who do not notice this think that "my child has become extremely stubborn and deaf" and complain. As a result of determining their own measures, the parent and the child cannot understand each other. As a result, cases of child's boredom with parents are observed.

Literature

1. Каршибаева Г. А. и др. Факторы суицидального поведения, влияющие на формирование подросткового поведения //Молодой ученый. – 2018. – №. 49. – С. 235-237.
2. Eshmurodov O. ЎЗБЕК ОИЛАСИ МУСТАҲКАМЛИГИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШДА МИЛЛИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРНИНГ ЎРНИ //Журнал Педагогика и психологии в современном образовании. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 6.
3. Eshmurodov O. ҚАЙНОНА ВА КЕЛИН ЎРТАСИДАГИ МУНОСАБАТЛАРНИНГ БОЛАЛАР ТАРБИЯСИГА ТАЪСИРИ //Журнал Педагогика и психологии в современном образовании. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 6.
4. Eshmurodov O. ОИЛА МУСТАҲКАМЛИГИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШНИНГ ИЖТИМОЙ-ПСИХОЛОГИК ОМИЛЛАРИ //Scienceweb academic papers collection. – 2022.
5. Eshmurodov O., Abdullayeva S. ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЕ САМООПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ И ВЫБОР ПРОФЕССИИ УЧАЩИМИСЯ В ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОМ ЗНАНИИ //Журнал Педагогика и психологии в современном образовании. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 2.
6. Eshmurodov O. OILAVIY MUNOSABATLAR BARQARORLASHSHUVIDA MILLIY QADRIYATLARINING AHAMIYATI //Журнал Педагогика и психологии в современном образовании. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 1.
7. Jabborov X., Eshmuradov O. ШАРҚ МУТАФАККИРЛАРИ ИШЛАРИДА МИЛЛИЙ ТАРБИЯ МАСАЛАСИ //Журнал Педагогика и психологии в современном образовании. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 2.
8. Elamanovich E. O. et al. SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS AFFECTING THE UPBRINGING OF CHILDREN IN FAMILY RELATIONSHIPS //Science and Innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 201-205.
9. Eshmurodov O., Fazliddinova U. OILADAGI IJTIMOY PSIXOLOGIK MUHITNING BARQARORLIGI TA'MINLASHDA QAYNONA VA KELIN MUNOSABATLARINING O 'RNI //Журнал Педагогика и психологии в современном образовании. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 1.
10. Eshmurodov O., Eshboyeva B. O 'SMIRLIK DAVRIDA JINSIY STERIOTIPLARNING YOSH XUSUSIYATLARI //Журнал Педагогика и психологии в современном образовании. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 2.
11. Eshmuradov O., Ismoilova G. OILAVIY MUNOSABATLARDA BOLALAR TA'RBIYASIGA TA'SIRI ETUVCHI IJTIMOY-PSIXOLOGIK OMILLAR //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. B4. – С. 201-205.
12. Тилакова М. А., Эшмуратов О. Э. КРЕАТИВ КОБИЛИЯТЛАРНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ МЕХАНИЗМЛАРИ //Scientific progress. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 143-149.
13. Elamanovich O. E. OILAVIY MUNOSABATLARDAGI NIZOLARNING KELIB CHIQISH SABABLARI //Archive of Conferences. – 2022. – С. 1-7.
14. Elamanovich E. O. OILA BARQARORLIGINI SHAKLLANTIRISH OMILLARI //Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 1318-1323.

15. Эшмурадов О. Э. ОИЛАВИЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАРДА ШАХС МОСЛАШУВЧАНЛИГИ ХУСУСИЯТИНИНГ ОИЛА МУСТАҲҚАМЛИГИГА ТАЪСИРИ: DOI: <https://doi.org/10.53885/edinres.2021.21.57.012> Эшмурадов Олмосбек Эламонович, Термиз давлат университетининг Педагогика институти Психология кафедраси катта ўқитувчиси //Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал. – 2021. – №. 1-Махсус сон. – С. 377-380.
16. Эшмурадов О. Э. Оилавий муҳит ва оилавий муносабатлар психологиянинг ўрганиш предмети сифатида //ЎзМУ хабарлари” Мирзо Улуғбек номидаги Ўзбекистон миллий университети илмий журнали. – 2019. – С. 162-164.
17. Eshmurodov O. E. SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF MAINTAINING FAMILY-MARRIAGE RELATIONS //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 10. – №. 12. – С. 803-807.
18. Uralovich T. F. Conducting classes on fine arts based on information and communication technologies //International Engineering Journal For Research & Development. – 2021. – Т. 6. – С. 3-3.
19. Toshpulatov F. Use of geometric patterns and their types from eliminations of drawing and applied art in architectural facilities //Физико-технологического образование. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1.
20. Urolovich T. F. et al. CHIZMA GEOMETRIYA TA'LIMI JARAYONIDA TALABALARNING MUSTAQIL TA'LIM FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISH //Евразийский журнал права, финансов и прикладных наук. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 279-283.
21. Toshpulatov F. U., Qizi R. F. G., Qizi R. Z. G. On Organizing and Supervising the Independent Work of Drawing Geometry Guidelines and General Rules //Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. – 2022. – Т. 14. – С. 83-86.
22. Toshpulatov F. OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA CHIZMACHILIK FANINI O 'QITISHNING HOZIRGI KUNDAGI HOLATI //Физико-технологического образование. – 2022. – №. 4.
23. Baratovna T. R., Abdurakhmanova S. LEGAL AND REGULATORY BASIS OF ORGANIZING ACTIVITY CENTERS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS //E Global Congress. – 2023. – Т. 2. – С. 65-68.
24. Турапова Р. Developing dialogic speech of pre-school children on the basis of a variative approach //Современные тенденции инновационного развития науки и образования в глобальном мире. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4.
25. Urolovich T. F. et al. SAN'AT INSON MEHNAT JARAYONINING AJRALMAS QISMI SIFATIDA //Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 592-594.
26. Toshpulatov F. U. et al. Issues of Developing the Culture of Measurement in Drawing Lessons (In the Case of General Secondary Schools) //Vital Annex: International Journal of Novel Research in Advanced Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 111-119.
27. Ra'no T., Maftuna B. Variative Approach Based on of Children Dialogic Speech Development Methodology Improvement //European Journal of Higher Education and Academic Advancement. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 99-104.

28. Toshpulatov F. Qadimiy grix va o 'simliksimon (Islimiy) naqsh elementlarining geometrik tahlili //Физико-технологического образование. – 2022. – №. 4.
29. Toshpulatov F. CHIZMACHILIK FANINI TABIIY HODISALAR BILAN AMALIY BOG'LIQLIGI //Физико-технологического образование. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1.
30. Urolovich T. F. CHIZMACHILIK DARSLARIDA AMALIY SAN'AT ELEMENTLARIDAN FOYDALANIB TARKIBIDA TUTASHMA ELEMENTLAR QATNASHGAN NAQSH NAMUNALARINI CHIZISH //Евразийский журнал права, финансов и прикладных наук. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 158-162.
31. Baratovna T. R., Asal A. " IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF CHILDREN'S DIALOGIC SPEECH DEVELOPMENT BASED ON A VARIATIONAL APPROACH"(IN THE CASE OF 5-6 YEAR OLD CHILDREN) //Conferencea. – 2023. – С. 45-51.
32. Urolovich T. F. METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPING AESTHETIC SKILLS IN FUTURE DRAWING TEACHERS //International Scientific and Current Research Conferences. – 2023. – С. 108-114.
33. Uralovich T. F. THE ROLE OF APPLIED ART IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF AESTHETIC SKILLS OF STUDENTS //International Journal of Advance Scientific Research. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 05. – С. 111-118.
34. Uralovich T. F. Conducting classes on fine arts based on information and communication technologies //International Engineering Journal For Research & Development. – 2021. – Т. 6. – С. 3-3.
35. Toshpo'Latov F. U. et al. Bolalarni o 'yin texnologiyalari asosida kasb-hunarga qiziqishlarini shakllantirishda rivojlantiruvchi o 'yinlar //Science and Education. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 487-491.
36. Турапова P. Developing dialogic speech of pre-school children on the basis of a variative approach //Современные тенденции инновационного развития науки и образования в глобальном мире. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4.
37. Fazilat B. et al. Methods of Involving Children who are Not Included in Pre-School Education Organizations to Private Pre-School Education Organizations //Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching. – 2023. – Т. 18. – С. 104-118.
38. Mushtariy S. et al. Ways of Using Games in Forming the Activity of Preschool Children //Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching. – 2023. – Т. 18. – С. 119-135.
39. Сайдуллаева М. Б., Маъруфжонова Р. Л. Эффективные способы организации обязательного однолетнего обучения детей 6-7 лет //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 2-2 (81). – С. 180-183.
40. qizi Saydillayeva M. B. PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALARNI QO 'LLASH ORQALI TA'LIM SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH USULLARI //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 1182-1187.
41. Сайдиллаева М. Effectiveness of variative development of educational programs in pedagogical processes //Общество и инновации. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 2/S. – С. 160-165.

42. Buriboyevna A. M. Conditions For Planning The Educational Process In A Preschool Institution With Compensatory Groups //Vital Annex: International Journal of Novel Research in Advanced Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 70-77.
43. Buriboyevna A. M. Recommendations for Improving the Quality of Preschool Education through an Assessment System //Vital Annex: International Journal of Novel Research in Advanced Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 5. – C. 297-304.